

The water balance of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced plants adapted to the steppe climate

Khromykh Nina, Didur Oleh

Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine)

Chaenomeles plants have long been used in traditional medicine (Yang et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2022) and have become widespread in Europe (Rumpunen, 2002), but have limited distribution in Ukraine (Lykholat et al., 2021). The introduction of plants into the steppe zone is complicated by the peculiarities of the climate (Khromykh et al., 2018), which is characterized by periods of drought during the growing season and frosty periods in winter. This creates specific requirements for the adaptive capabilities of plants, in particular their ability to regulate their water regime.

Water metabolism is essential for many physiological processes of plants (photosynthesis, respiration, enzymatic catalysis, etc.), and even a slight disturbance in it changes the normal course of metabolic processes, which negatively affects plant productivity (Dolgova et al., 2003; Musienko, 2005). Changes in the water regime of plants can be characterized by a set of indicators, including the intensity of transpiration and the level of water deficit (Lykholat, 1999, 2003). These indicators can increase or decrease depending on the intensity of the influence of environmental factors, primarily air temperature and soil moisture content (Lyashok et al., 2006; Ponomaryova, 2011; Zandalinas et al., 2017).

The course and outcome of plant introduction are also largely determined by the moisture availability (Dolgova et al., 2003; Zaitseva, 2017). Therefore, the assessment of the adaptation success of introduced plants to new growth conditions should be made taking into account the studying the plants ability to regulate water balance during the growing season.

The research was conducted in 2018 on the territory of the Botanical Garden of Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, where plants of the genus *Chaenomeles* Lindl. were introduced more than twenty years ago and have been actively fruiting during the recent period. The objects of the research were some species and hybrids: *Ch. japonica*, *Ch. speciosa*, *Ch. cathayensis*, *Ch. × superba*, and *Ch. × californica*.

To assess the water balance of introduced plants during the growing season, the intensity of transpiration and the level of water deficit in the leaves of plants of the same age were determined within one experimental plot, in the time interval from 11:00 to 11:30 on sunny days. The daily water deficit in the leaves of introduced plants was determined under contrasting moisture supply conditions, which occurred in early June (wet period), early August (dry period), and mid-August during the heavy rainfall (moisture restoration period).

According to the results obtained, the level of precipitation in late May – early June was sufficient, so the moisture deficit in the leaves of plants of all *Chaenomeles* species and hybrids was insignificant (Table 1).

The level of water deficit in the leaves of all introduced plants during the wet period of vegetation was within the permissible physiological limits (less than 10%).

In the dry period, even the highest level of water deficit (19.21% in the leaves of *Ch. × californica*) did not cross the critical limit of 25% water loss by plants.

During the period of restoration of moisture supply in the leaves of all studied species and hybrids, the level of water deficit decreased, but the lack of moisture persisted, most of all in the leaves of *Ch. cathayensis* and *Ch. × californica*.

Table 1

Dynamics of the water deficit indicators (%) in leaves of the genus *Chaenomeles* introduced plants during the growing season in 2018 ($n = 30, x \pm SD$)

Period	Wet			Dry			Recovery		
Date	04.06	05.06	06.06	03.09	04.09	05.09	13.09	14.09	15.09
T, °C	26	27	23	31	31	27	25	25	18
Humidity, %	45	51	65	15	19	30	57	57	88
Water deficit indicators in plant leaves, % of full water saturation									
<i>Ch. japonica</i>	8.48 ± 0.04	8.57 ± 0.06	8.08 ± 0.07	20.98 ± 0.09	18.39 ± 0.16	17.17 ± 0.23	11.63 ± 0.19	11.27 ± 0.14	10.69 ± 0.18
Average for the period	8.38 ± 0.23 ^a			18.85 ± 0.76 ^b			11.19 ± 0.55 ^c		
<i>Ch. cathayensis</i>	6.40 ± 0.01	6.24 ± 0.03	6.11 ± 0.01	18.32 ± 0.09	17.35 ± 0.08	16.35 ± 0.08	14.49 ± 0.36	14.41 ± 0.37	12.42 ± 0.28
Average for the period	6.25 ± 0.13 ^a			17.34 ± 0.85 ^b			13.78 ± 1.06 ^c		
<i>Ch. speciosa</i>	9.30 ± 0.11	9.25 ± 0.08	9.14 ± 0.02	18.61 ± 0.11	18.36 ± 0.06	17.32 ± 0.07	12.64 ± 0.11	11.57 ± 0.13	10.65 ± 0.13
Average for the period	9.23 ± 0.10 ^a			18.10 ± 1.09 ^b			11.62 ± 0.87 ^c		
<i>Ch. × superba</i>	9.35 ± 0.07	9.72 ± 0.12	8.72 ± 0.11	21.02 ± 0.29	17.59 ± 0.13	17.24 ± 0.12	13.89 ± 0.13	13.52 ± 0.17	13.33 ± 0.12
Average for the period	9.26 ± 0.45 ^a			18.62 ± 2.04 ^b			13.58 ± 0.34 ^c		
<i>Ch. × californica</i>	8.17 ± 0.07	8.22 ± 0.03	7.93 ± 0.08	19.82 ± 0.10	19.53 ± 0.14	18.28 ± 0.17	15.26 ± 0.06	15.43 ± 0.17	14.29 ± 0.24
Average for the period	8.10 ± 0.14 ^a			19.21 ± 1.21 ^b			14.99 ± 0.45 ^c		

Note. Different letters in a row indicate statistically significant differences in the means of the pair being compared, according to the Tukey test ($P < 0.05$).

In general, the fastest restoration of water balance after drought and the most effective regulation of transpiration intensity with the onset of the drought period and after its end were observed in the leaves of *Ch. japonica*, *Ch. speciosa*, and *Ch. × superba* plants.

REFERENCES

- Dolhova, L. H., Demura, T. A., & Koval, I. V. (2003). Osoblyvosti vodnoho obminu roslyn-introducentiv rodu *Rosa* L. [Peculiarities of water metabolism of introduced plants of the genus *Rosa* L.]. *Visnyk of Dnipropetrovsk University. Biology, ecology*, 11(2), 28–32 (in Ukrainian)
- Khromykh, N., Lykholat, Y., Shupranova, L., Kabar, A., Didur, O., Lykholat, T., & Kulbachko, Y. (2018). Interspecific differences of antioxidant ability of introduced *Chaenomeles* species with respect to adaptation to the steppe zone conditions. *Biosystems Diversity*, 26(2), 132–138.
- Liashok, A. K., Hryhoriuk, I. P., Feoktysov, P. O. (2006). Avtokolyvalni protsesy vodoobminu roslyn [Self-oscillating processes of water exchange in plants]. Logos, Kyiv (in Ukrainian).
- Lykholat, Y. V. (1999). Ekoloho-fiziolohichni osoblyvosti bahatorichnykh dernoutvoriuiuchykh zlakiv tekhnohennykh terytorii [Ecological and physiological features of

perennial sodforming cereals of technogenic territories]. Dnipropetrovsk University Press, Dnipropetrovsk (in Ukrainian).

Lykholat, Y. V. (2003). Vodnyi obmin dernoutvoriuiuchykh trav, shcho zrostaiut u shtuchnykh fitotsenozakh [Water exchange of sod-forming grasses growing in artificial phytocenoses]. *Visnyk Donetskoho universytetu. Ser. A. Pryrodnychi nauky*, 1, 288–290 (in Ukrainian).

Lykholat, Y. V., Khromykh, N. O., Didur, O. O., Okovytyy, S. I., Sklyar, T. V., Davydov, V. R., Lykholat, T. Y., & Kovalenko, I. M. (2021). Soluble cuticular wax composition and antimicrobial activity of the fruits of *Chaenomeles* species and an interspecific hybrid. *Biosystems Diversity*, 29(4), 334–339. doi: 10.15421/012142

Ma, Y., Li, J., Li, J., Yang, L., Wu, G., & Liu, S. (2022). Comparative metabolomics study of *Chaenomeles speciosa* (Sweet) Nakai from different geographical regions. *Foods* (Basel, Switzerland), 11(7), 1019.

Musiienko, M. M. (2005). Fiziolohiia roslyn [Physiology of plants]. Lybid, Kyiv (in Ukrainian).

Ponomaryova, O. A. (2011). Vodnyi obmin derev rodu *Tilia* L. v umovakh stepovoi zony Ukrainy [Water exchange of trees of genus *Tilia* L. in the conditions of a steppe zone of Ukraine]. *Visnyk Dnipropetrovskoho derzhavnoho ahrarnoho universytetu*, 2, 46–50 (in Ukrainian).

Rumpunen K. (2002). *Chaenomeles*: Potential new fruit crop for Northern Europe. In J. Janick, A. Whipkey (Eds.), *Trends in new crops and new uses* (pp. 385–392). Alexandria, ASHS Press

Yang, L., Ahmed, S., Stepp, J. R., Zhao, Y., Zeng, M. J., Pei, S., Xue, D., & Xu, G. (2015). Cultural uses, ecosystem services, and nutrient profile of flowering quince (*Chaenomeles speciosa*) in the highlands of Western Yunnan, China. *Economic Botany*, 69(3), 273–283.

Zaitceva, I. O. (2017). Kilkisna otsinka posukhostiikosti introdutsentiv rodu *Syringa* L. v umovakh stepovoho Prydniprovia [Quantitative estimation of drought-resistance of introduced plants genus *Syringa* L. in steppe right bank of Dnipro]. *Issues of steppe forestry and forest reclamation of soils*, 46, 76–81 (in Ukrainian).

Zandalinas, S. I., Mittler, R., Balfagón, D., Arbona, V., & Gómez-Cadenas, A. (2018). Plant adaptations to the combination of drought and high temperatures. *Physiologia plantarum*, 162(1), 2–12.

Zhang, X., Bian, Z., Li, S., Chen, X., & Lu, C. (2019). Comparative analysis of phenolic compound profiles, antioxidant capacities, and expressions of phenolic biosynthesis-related genes in soybean microgreens grown under different light spectra. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 67(49), 13577–13588.